

DEVELOPMENT OF LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN IELTS

Mukhammadiyeva Risola,

teacher of Faculty of English Language and Literature of the Navoi State

Pedagogical Institute

Dzhanzakova NurAsel Ganievna,

2nd year student of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Faculty of English Language

and Literature

Abstract: The article describes the rules for developing listening comprehension in the IELTS exam, and how students should work on it. It also talks about achieving a higher level in the IELTS exam.

Keywords: IELTS, Microsoft Excel, BBC, CNN, TED, interview transcript, subtitle.

Аннотация: В статье описаны правила развития аудирования на экзамене IELTS и то, как студенты должны над ним работать. Здесь также говорится о достижении более высокого уровня на экзамене IELTS.

Ключевые слова: IELTS, Microsoft Excel, BBC, CNN, TED, стенограмма интервью, подзаголовки.

In this modern era, the English language is attracting relatively more attention, particularly among youths. This phenomenon can easily be defined with the opportunities that come after it. Listening comprehension is considered as one of the most important skills which students need while learning English, communicating with people, and at the same time getting a high score in the IELTS exam. For this, students need to develop English listening skills through various methods, tips, and techniques. For the students who have decided to study IELTS test at home independently, bellow given some recommended exercises to improve their listening skills. These are the listening tips on the International English Assessment System that are important to master.

Tip 1. Correct spelling

Almost half of the questions in all IELTS listening tests are fill-in-the-blank questions. That's why you have to write the words correctly!

One of the ways my students improve their spelling is to download and use a spelling quiz program. This is a Microsoft Excel file where you can create your own spelling checks so you can focus on practicing those hard-to-pronounce words.

You can also use our FREE online IELTS course on Quizlet (<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.quizlet.quizletandroid>). There you will find word lists for many common IELTS topics, with spelling and definition exercises for each word list.

Remember, names are more likely to be correct answers to fill-in-the-blank questions on the IELTS List test, so focus on practicing spelling names!

If your text is hard to read, it's no wonder it's considered "wrong"!

Also, if the IELTS examiner does not understand what you wrote on the answer sheet on the day of the test, some of your answers may be considered "wrong" because they cannot read them clearly!

Tip 2. Practice reading while listening

Another way to improve your IELTS skills is to practice listening and reading at the same time. To practice this, find a BBC or CNN news video you haven't listened to before (and you can also use a TED Talk) and turn on subtitles or closed captioning. Play the video and try to read the subtitles during the conversation. This will help you improve your reading speed, which will benefit you when scanning the IELTS List questions and answer options during the test.

Tip 3. Learn to use common IELTS accents!

Because the IELTS test was created in the UK, IELTS List's test uses different slang and dialects in podcasts that are common in countries closely associated with the UK. It is rare (but not impossible!) to hear different accents in official IELTS listening tests.

To better understand these accents, we recommend that you start listening and watching the news of specific countries. Two of the best organizations to visit are the BBC and CNN. Both these news organizations have news pages from different regions and countries. So, you need to increase your confidence in your listening practice.

Tip 4. Analyze transcripts for "information changes" in IELTS interviews.

So you'll want to practice listening to these IELTS Conversation Variations, Arguments and Misunderstandings in Sections 1 and 3 of the IELTS Listening Test. Listen to as many IELTS conversations as you can, and practice noticing changes in the speakers' tone of voice.

After listening to your IELTS interview, review the interview transcript and see if there are any other tips that you didn't notice before. You will often hear speakers giving information about what to say and how to say it in IELTS interviews!

Speeches given in TED talks can help too!

You can also use TED talks to hear how people use their voices to show that something they're saying is wrong, whether an idea they disagree with or a point they're trying to make is wrong. Seeing how these intonation changes are used in the real world will make them a little easier to spot on the IELTS List tests!

Tip 5. Learn to take notes to improve your quick analysis skills.

In the IELTS List exam, you have to simultaneously 1) listen to a conversation or lecture, 2) look at the questions and answers, and 3) analyze what you hear, so you need to work on developing your listening, reading and thinking skills.

One way to do this is to practice taking notes while listening to IELTS talks and lectures. Although you may not have much time to take test notes, adding notes to your IELTS preparation plan can help you develop the concentration and analysis skills needed for the IELTS exam.

When you receive notes, you need to quickly analyze what you hear. It also helps to concentrate in conversations and lectures. You can also review your notes against

IELTS interview and lecture transcripts to check that your notes match what was actually said.

Increase the "game speed" as an additional task!

As a challenge, some students may speed up the conversation or lecture they are listening to. You can do this by going to the sound "settings" and changing the speed to "1.20" or even "1.5". It encourages you to write faster, process what you hear faster, and notice intonation faster. Also, if you go back to listening to the audio at "normal" speed, it's a little easier to understand!

In conclusion, don't forget to improve your IELTS listening skills, use the 3×3 method to improve your English listening, reading and comprehension skills quickly. Watch BBC or CNN news videos to get a better understanding of the different accents you might hear on IELTS test day and how they use intonation and tempo to emphasize information. Practice correct spelling and writing and take notes in IELTS talks and lectures to improve your ability to focus on what you hear. Practice using these techniques many times before your IELTS test and you will see how your IELTS Listening score will be improved!

REFERENCES:

1. J. Jalilov. Foreign language teaching methodology, Tashkent, 2012
2. Djumakulov A. A. The difference modular teaching technology and traditional teaching, 2020.
3. Vanessa Jakeman and Clare McDowell. "Insight into IELTS" 2018
4. Jalolov D.D., Methodological development for group leaders